

Residual levels of plant protection products in honey do not pose a health risk

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In June 2016, various media reported on residues of plant protection products in honeys. The applicable maximum residue levels were not reached or exceeded in any of the honey samples. Despite this, the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) made a health assessment of the measured residues and comes to the conclusion that a health risk is unlikely to result from the consumption of honey containing residues in the reported concentrations.

To make the health assessment of the residue levels, the BfR compared the measured levels with the “acute reference doses” for the two active substances. The acute reference dose (ARfD) is defined by the WHO as the quantity of a substance that a consumer can ingest with food in the course of a day in one or several meals without any recognisable health risks. In this particular instance, each respective acute reference dose for the corresponding active substance is exhausted to less than 1 %, even when the honeys with the highest measured residue levels are consumed.

This text version is a translation of the original German text which is the only legally binding version.

The full version of this BfR Information is available in German on

<http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/rueckstandsgehalte-von-pflanzenschutzmitteln-in-honig-stellen-kein-gesundheitsrisiko-dar.pdf>

About the BfR

The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) is a scientifically independent institution within the portfolio of the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL) in Germany. It advises the Federal Government and Federal Laender on questions of food, chemical and product safety. The BfR conducts its own research on topics that are closely linked to its assessment tasks.